

CHIBA
UNIVERSITY

Multi Sensor Optical Modules for IceCube Gen-2

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ICECUBE GEN2

DETECTORS SURFACE • RADIO • OPTICAL

Cosmic Ray Surface Array

An air shower array that sits on top of the optical array
One surface station installed above each optical string

IceCube-Gen2 Optical Module

4x the sensitivity of IceCube's modules
9,600 new optical modules in total to be deployed in the ice

50 m

1370 m

2780 m

IceCube-Gen2:
120 new strings of optical modules

IceCube:
86 strings of optical modules

DeepCore

Antarctic bedrock

IceCube
(1 km)

Amundsen-Scott South Pole Station, Antarctica

A National Science Foundation-managed research facility

Below-Ice Radio Array

361 detector stations spread over an area of 500 km²

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

an Upgraded detector with unique features

Credit: S. Niedworok/DESY

mDOM

24x 3" PMTs & dia. 36 cm

Credit: N. Shimizu/ICEHAP

D-Egg

2x 8" HQE PMTs & dia. 30 cm

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

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LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

An Upgraded detector with unique features

- **Overview**
- Designed for Gen2 by optimising and combining DEgg and mDOM features
- Modularised Optical-Mechanical Assembly Structure with Multi-PMT Design (16/18 PMT Option)
- Common Bus system infrastructure to Upgrade (PCA/MMB)

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

An Upgraded detector with unique features

- **Electronics**
- WuBases (Waveform Micro Base): Dedicated Modular High Voltage boards with pulse shaping waveform recording and low level hitbuffer processing
- Fanout Board: Fanout for PMTs channels and multiplexer logic circuitry for data selection
- MiniMain Boards: Power and Communication Boards to Surface (Based on IceCube ICM)

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

An Upgraded detector with unique features

- **PMTs**
- Multi 4-inch bespoke 13-stage PMTs to fit compact design
- First IceCube Module to employ both Hamamatsu and NNVT PMTs (helps inform performance, R&D, and scalability for Gen2)
- Operational Voltage at photocathode $\sim 900\text{-}1100\text{ V}$, $>25\%$ Quantum Efficiency, Selected Nominal Gain 5×10^6

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

An Upgrade detector with unique features

- **Mechanics/Optics**
- Gel pad technology: PMTs supported by optical gel coupling to glass and minimal shadowing support structures for enhanced performance
- Harness: Segmented Harness Design with slotting guides for maximal support whilst reducing shadowing
- Flashers: Repurposed flashers from mDOMs for in ice-calibration
- Pressure Vessel: Glass Housing Optical Modules

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

PMT Signal Capturing

- TTS of the system is dominated by PMT TTS
- Due to power consumption and scattering in-ice, analog signals are shaped/broadened

O(few ns) \rightarrow FWHM 30 ns

- Then they are digitised and reconstructed using a well-known pulse template as shown
- This results in a true SPE timing resolution of $\sigma_{Transit\ Time} \sim 2.5$ ns, as required for Gen2

(a) SPE waveform

LOMs (Long Optical Modules)

Dual Channel Data Acquisition

- Dual Channel (Ch1 = Anode + Ch2 = Dynode 8) Readout
- Electronics carefully tuned to keep ch1/ch2 overlap and achieve good dynamic range, Comparator output set to 0.2PE triggering circular memory buffers that record between SPE and 5000PE/25ns

LOM Production and Testing

From Cradle to Data

A circular metal instrument, likely a neutrino detector component, is suspended in a hole drilled through a thick ice sheet. The instrument has a central hub with several cables and wires extending from it. The ice surrounding the hole is clear and shows concentric rings of drilling. The text on the right side of the image provides context for the upgrade work being performed.

Upgrade
Begins!

3/7 strings
Deployed

And our
Gen2 hats
Are on!

Acceptance Testing for Pole

Schedule

Acceptance Testing

Measurements: Gain

- All modules are tested in both lab and on the ice before deployment in Ice
- Right shows PMT charge distributions per PMT measurements in units of Dynode 10 Voltage

$$V_{10} \sim 70v - 90v$$

$$\Leftrightarrow V_K \sim 840v - 1080v$$

Acceptance Testing

Measurements: Gain

- SPE gain calibration measurement shown for one of the LOM-16s as an example
- Amplifiers are configured so that SPE or narrow pulses are digitised over several samples with FWHM of 30 ns and a well-defined SPE template is used for both channels

Acceptance Testing

Measurements: Dual Channel scaling

- We flash internal LEDs and measure the charge ratio between Dynode 8 and Anode
- By Scanning LEDs intensities we simultaneously test LED drive circuit performance and linearity

Acceptance Testing

Measurements: Channel Time Offset pre-calibration

Flasher testing
(All 8 flash together)

$$\text{Time Offset} = (\text{Fitted arrival time}) - (\text{Recorded flasher time}) - (\text{delays due to processing})$$

Acceptance Testing

Measurements: Channel Time Offset pre-calibration

- LOM transit time =
(Fitted arrival time)
- (Recorded flasher time)
 - (delays due to processing)

And Gen2 DOM design is in progress!

Automating Multiple-PMT testing

2025

Angular Acceptance/Uniformity

Commissing Updated Boards

Possible develop ASIC

boards for mass production

WuBase Updating
in collaboration with
Chiang Mai University/
HANA

Gen2 Candidate Glass
Testing

2026

Fully unify Gen2 DOM design

Nov: Design Verification Test (DVT)

2027

June: Acceptance Testing

Nov: Final Design Review & Design

2028

October: Gen2 Mass Production Start!

Summary

- Multi optical sensor modules will enable the detection of high energy neutrinos in the next generation Ice Cherenkov telescopes
- The IceCube Upgrade, including 12 LOMs, will be deployed will give us crucial insight into the R&D of the Gen2 DOM, which is already underway
- We require a factor 4 improvement in the effective area, which our candidates already provide
- It is a really exciting time for our collaboration as we aim to measure GeV-ZeV neutrinos in just the next few years, and we look forward to the prospects Gen2 will bring for high energy neutrino and multimessenger astronomy!

Thank you!

